

Supplementary material for:

Auguy F, Chéron S, Dossou L, Pinel-Galzi A, Thomas E, Aribi J, Celli MG, Cunnac S, Hébrard E, Albar L (2026) eIFiso4G editing confers high and broad-spectrum resistance against rice yellow mottle virus. bioRxiv, ver.2 peer-reviewed and recommended by PCI Plants <https://doi.org/10.64898/2026.01.30.702252>

[Sup. Data 1](#) - Sequences of the eIFiso4G1 and eIFiso4G2 protein in the Kitaake variety and in the different mutant lines.

[Sup. Table 1](#) - Number and genotypes of T0 and T2 plants obtained with the different constructs.

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[Sup. Fig. 8](#) - Conformational variability in the predicted 3D structures of the MIF4G domain for the *rymv1-3* allele.

Sup. Data 1- Sequences of the eIFiso4G1 and eIFiso4G2 protein in the Kitaake variety and in the different mutant lines. Differences with the Kitaake wild type sequence are underlined in red.

>eIFiso4G1-Kitaake

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LKDVISLIFEKAVFEPTFCMPYAQLCSDLNEKLPSPFPSEEPGGKEITFKRVLLNNCQEA~~F~~E~~G~~A~~E~~S~~L~~R~~A~~E~~I~~A~~K~~L~~T~~G~~P~~D~~Q~~E~~M~~
ERRDKERIVKLR~~T~~LGNIRLIGELLKQKMVPEKIVHHIVQELLSGSPDKKACPEEENVEAICQFFNTIGKQDENPKSRRI
NDTYFIQMKELTTNLQ~~L~~APRLRFMVRD~~V~~DLRSNNWVPRREEIKAKTISEIHDEAMKTLGLRPGATGLTRNGRNAPGGPL
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
GIRILDEAQQCIEELQCPEYYSEIVKEAINLALDKGNFIDPLVRLLEHLHAKKIFKTEDLKTGCLLYAALLEDIGIDL
LAPALFGEVVARLSLSCGLSFEVVEEILKAVEDTYFRKGI~~F~~DAVMKTMGGNSSGQAILSSHAVVIDACNKLK*

>eIFiso4G1-KO3

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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
GIRILDEAQQCIEELQCPEYYSEIVKEAINLALDKGNFIDPLVRLLEHLHAKKIFKTEDLKTGCLLYAALLEDIGIDL
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KDCQTKNTWKYPSNW*

>eIFiso4G1-KO8

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ERRDKERIVKLR~~T~~LGNIRLIGELLKQKMVPEKIVHHIVQELLSGSPDKKACPEEENVEAICQFFNTIGKQDENPKSRRI
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
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FDWP*

>eIFiso4G1-KO11

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QQEQVNRQDQLNHQFASKAQVGPPTALIKAEVPSARRGNLSEKDRVLKTVKGI~~LNKLTPEKFDLLKQG~~LME~~SGIT~~TADI
LKDVISLIFEKAVFEPTFCMPYAQLCSDLNEKLPSPFPSEEPGGKEITFKRVLLNNCQEA~~F~~E~~G~~A~~E~~S~~L~~R~~A~~E~~I~~A~~K~~L~~T~~G~~P~~D~~Q~~E~~M~~
ERRDKERIVKLR~~T~~LGNIRLIGELLKQKMVPEKIVHHIVQELLSGSPDKKACPEEENVEAICQFFNTIGKQDENPKSRRI
NDTYFIQMKELTTNLQ~~L~~APRLRFMVRD~~V~~DLRSNNWVPRREEIKAKTISEIHDEAMKTLGLRPGATGLTRNGRNAPGGPL
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
GIRILDEAQQCIEELQCPEYYSEIVKEAINLALDKGNFIDPLVRLLEHLHAKKIFKTEDLKTGCLLYAALLEDIGIDL
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GP*

>eIFiso4G1-dell

MEKDHQPVISLRPGGGGGGPRPGRFLSPAFAAAAASGSGDLLRSHVGGASKIGDPNFVFRVRYTRDQLELREIVDIPE
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QQEQVNRQDQLNHQFASKAQVGPPTALIKAEVPSARRGNLSEKDRVLKTVKGI~~LNKLTPEKFDLLKQG~~LME~~SGIT~~TADI
LKDVISLIFEKAVFEPTFCMPYAQLCSDLNEKLPSPFPSEEPGGKEITFKRVLLNNCQEA~~F~~E~~G~~A~~E~~S~~L~~R~~A~~E~~I~~A~~K~~L~~T~~G~~P~~D~~Q~~E~~M~~
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NDTYFIQMKELTTNLQ~~L~~APRLRFMVRD~~V~~DLRSNNWVPRREEIKAKTISEIHDEAMKTLGLRPGATGLTRNGRNAPGGPL
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
GIRILDEAQQCIEELQCPEYYSEIVKEAINLALDKGNFIDPLVRLLEHLHAKKIFKTEDLKTGCLLYAALLEDIGIDL
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IV - - TGPDEM

>eIFiso4G1-del2

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AILLRINQEI~~DI~~ELHGEDIWGRPESDVQVQTQTQAQPHNRYGETDNRDWRARTVQPPAANEKSWDNIREAKAAHASSGR
QQEQVNRQDQLNHQFASKAQVGPPTALIKAEVPSARRGNLSEKDRVLKTVKGI~~LNKLTPEKFDLLKQG~~LME~~SGIT~~TADI
LKDVISLIFEKAVFEPTFCMPYAQLCSDLNEKLPSPFPSEEPGGKEITFKRVLLNNCQEA~~F~~E~~G~~A~~E~~S~~L~~R~~A~~E~~I~~A~~K~~L~~T~~G~~P~~D~~Q~~E~~M~~
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
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LAPALFGEVVARLSLSCGLSFEVVEEILKAVEDTYFRKGI~~F~~DAVMKTMGGNSSGQAILSSHAVVIDACNKLK*
IAM - TGPDEM

>eIFiso4G1-del3

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QQEQVNRQDQLNHQFASKAQVGPPTALIKAEVPSARRGNLSEKDRVLKTVKGI~~LNKLTPEKFDLLKQG~~LME~~SGIT~~TADI
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ERRDKERIVKLR~~T~~LGNIRLIGELLKQKMVPEKIVHHIVQELLSGSPDKKACPEEENVEAICQFFNTIGKQDENPKSRRI
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PHGSGALIGKSALLGSGGPPSRPSSLMASLTHTPAQTAPSPKPVSAAPAVVPVTDKAAGSSHEMPAAVQKKT~~V~~S~~L~~L~~E~~E~~E~~Y~~F~~
GIRILDEAQQCIEELQCPEYYSEIVKEAINLALDKGNFIDPLVRLLEHLHAKKIFKTEDLKTGCLLYAALLEDIGIDL
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AK - TGPDEM

>eIFiso4G1-del4

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>eIFiso4G1-del6

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QQEQVNRQDQLNHQFASKAQVGPPTALIKAEVPSARRGNLSEKDRVLKTVKGI LNKLTPKFDLLKGQLMESGIT TADI
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>eIFiso4G1-del7

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>eIFiso4G1-del9

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>eIFiso4G2-Kitaake

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>eIFiso4G2-KO1

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KSPDYYPVVEKAINLALDKGTNSIDPLRLLEHLYNKNVFKATDLETGCLLYSLLDELAI DLPKPAVHFGEVIGRVLV
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>eIFiso4G2-KO2

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>eIFiso4G2-KO3

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Sup. Table 1 - Number and genotypes of T0 and T2 plants obtained with the different constructs.

	OseIFiso4G1			OseIFiso4G2
	p-iso4G1.1	p-iso4G1.2	p-iso4G1.3	p-iso4G2
T0 transgenic plants	45	27	18	4
T0 edited plants	37	16	13	2
Independent T0 with mutations leading to premature stop codon	11	5	1	3
substitution and/or in-frame deletion	5	1	5	0
T2 selected for further characterization with KO mutations	2	1	0	3
with substitution and/or in-frame deletion	3	0	4	0

Sup. Table 2 - Segregation of KO and WT alleles in F2 populations derived from crosses between eIFiso4G1 KO and eIFiso4G2 KO lines. The number of plants observed and the confidence interval (CI) of the percentage (binomial test, $p=0,95$) is given for each genotype. For comparison, the expected percentage is indicated into brackets. A total of 434 plants have been analysed and derived from crosses iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO2 (82 plants), iso4G1-KO11 x iso4G2-KO1 (88 plants), iso4G2-KO2 x iso4G1-KO11 (88 plants), iso4G2-KO3 x iso4G1-KO8 (88 plants), iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO3 (88 plants).

Genotype on OseIFiso4G2	Genotype on OseIFiso4G1			
	homozygous WT	heterozygous	homozygous KO	all
homozygous WT	53 plants CI: 9-16 % (6,25 % expected)	77 plants CI: 14-22 % (12,5 % expected)	10 plants CI: 1-4 % (6,25 % expected)	140 plants CI: 28-37 % (25 % expected)
heterozygous	87 plants CI: 16-24 % (12,5 % expected)	120 plants CI: 23-32 % (25 % expected)	11 plants CI: 1-5 % (12,5 % expected)	218 plants CI: 45-55 % (50 % expected)
homozygous KO	42 plants CI: 7-13 % (6,25 % expected)	34 plants CI: 5-11 % (12,5 % expected)	0 plants CI: 0-1 % (6,25 % expected)	76 plants CI: 14-21 % (25 % expected)
all	182 plants CI: 37-47 % (25 % expected)	231 plants CI: 48-58 % (50 % expected)	21 plants CI: 3-7 % (25 % expected)	434 plants

Sup. Table 3 - Grain filling rate in F2 plants and germination rate in F3 progenies derived from crosses between eIFiso4G1 KO and eIFiso4G2 KO lines. The grain filling rate was measured on F2 plants homozygous for a KO mutation in one *OseIFiso4G* copy and heterozygous for the other and compared to the expected 75% germination rate if the absence of double mutants were due to female sterility or embryo abortion. The germination rate of F3 progenies was compared to the expected 75% rate if the absence of double mutants were due to a germination defect. Significant differences are indicated by "*" (one-sided binomial test, $p < 0.05$).

Cross	F2 mother plant			F3 progeny	
	Genotype on <i>OseIFiso4G1</i>	Genotype on <i>OseIFiso4G2</i>	Grain filling rate (Filled grains / Total grains counted)	Germination rate	Segregation
iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO3	KO3/WT	KO3/KO3	0,92* (166/181)	0,71 (89/125)	77 iso4G1-htz / iso4G2-KO 60 iso4G1-KO / iso4G2-KO 0 iso4G1-KO / iso4G2-KO
iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO3	KO3/KO3	KO3/WT	0,93* (231/249)	0,9* 113/125)	-
iso4G1-KO11 x iso4G2-KO2	KO11/WT	KO2/KO2	0,88* (287/324)	0,88* (67/76)	-
iso4G1-KO11 x iso4G2-KO2	KO11/KO11	KO2/WT	0,86* (149/174)	0,82 (51/62)	-
iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO2	KO3/WT	KO2/KO2	0,82 (90/110)	0,94* (77/82)	-
iso4G1-KO3 x iso4G2-KO2	KO3/KO3	KO2/WT	0,86* (89/103)	0,47 (28/59)	-

Sup. Table 4 - Resistance-breaking rates on OseIFiso4G1 KO lines. Resistance-breaking rates was estimated by the number of plants detected positive with ELISA on leaf samples collected 8 weeks after inoculation with RYMV isolates Ng106, Ng119 or Tg247. Within plant sets inoculated with the same isolate, same letters indicated non significantly different proportions, estimated based on a Fisher exact test.

Lines	Ng106	Ng119	Tg247
iso4G1-KO3	0/60 ^a	0/85 ^a	0/96 ^a
iso4G1-KO8	0/60 ^a	0/71 ^a	0/96 ^a
iso4G1-KO1	0/60 ^a	0/76 ^a	0/96 ^a
<i>O. sativa</i> Gigante (rymv1.2)	2/59 ^a	64/81 ^b	0/96 ^a
<i>O. glaberrima</i> Tog5681 (rymv1.3)	31/61 ^b	67/78 ^b	20/91 ^b

Sup. Table 5 - Residues involved in key salt-bridges within the VPg central helix-MIF4G hairpin complex. Color intensity reflects the number of models in which a salt-bridge was predicted between each MIF4G residue and the corresponding VPg residue listed in the first column. MIF4G residue numbering refers to the full-length OseIFiso4G1 protein.

VPg residues	MIF4G residues			
	Kitaake WT	iso4G1-del4	iso4G1-del6	iso4G1-del7
38	324		317	
46	250	243		
		250	250	243
48	309	298		298
		309	309	309
50		243		243
52	309	298	309	298
				309
56	301	298		298
		301	301	301

Sup. Table 6 - Summary of phenotypic traits in the edited lines. Resistance was primarily assessed with the BF1 isolate and resistance to Cia, Tz11, Mg1 and Ng106 isolates was only assessed on lines resistant to BF1, and the control. Resistance breaking by Ng106, Ng119 and Tg247 was tested for KO lines in *OseIFiso4G1*, using varieties Gigante and Tog5681 carrying resistance alleles *rymv1-2* and *rymv1-3* as controls. Developmental traits were assessed relative to the wild type.

Lines	Resistance			Resistance-breaking			Developmental traits	
	BF1	Cia, Tz11	Mg1, Ng106	Ng106	Ng119	Tg247	plant height	tillering and panicle weight
WT	no	no	no	-	-	-	-	-
iso4G1-KO3	high	high	high	not detected	not detected	not detected	mild	not detected
iso4G1-KO8	high	high	high	not detected	not detected	not detected	mild	not detected
iso4G1-KO11	high	high	high	not detected	not detected	not detected	mild	not detected
iso4G1-del1	no	-	-	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del2	no	-	-	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del3	no	-	-	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del4	high	high	high	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del6	high	high	high	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del7	partial	partial	no	-	-	-	not detected	not detected
iso4G1-del9	no	-	-	-	-	-	mild	not detected
iso4G2-KO1	no	-	-	-	-	-	mild	not detected
iso4G2-KO2	no	-	-	-	-	-	moderate	not detected
iso4G2-KO3	no	-	-	-	-	-	moderate	not detected
Tog5681	high ¹	high ¹	high ¹	frequent	frequent	frequent	-	-
Gigante	high ¹	high ¹	high ¹	rare	frequent	not detected	-	-

¹- indicates phenotypic traits that have not been assessed

¹according to Hébrard E, Pinel-Galzi AA, Oludare A, Poulicard N, Aribi J, Fabre S, Issaka S, Mariac CC, Dereeper A, Albar L, Silue D, Fargette DJ (2018) Identification of a hypervirulent pathotype of Rice yellow mottle virus : a threat to genetic resistance deployment in West-Central Africa. *Phytopathology*, 108, 299–307. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-05-17-0190-R>

Sup. Fig. 1. Expression level of OseIFiso4G1 in lines with deletions in the central domain of the gene. Relative expression of OseIFiso4G1 was determined by RT-qPCR using actin as reference. Two or three biological replicates were used for each line. No significant difference between lines was detected with a Kruskal-Wallis test (p -value = 0.3).

Sup. Fig. 2. Resistance of edited lines against BF1 isolate of RYMV.

Resistance was evaluated based on the symptoms observed 11 and 18 DAI and ELISA on leaf samples collected 13 (experiment 2) or 15 (experiment 1) DAI. ELISA was not performed on the third experiment. Kitaake wild-type and IR64 were used as susceptibility control ; IR64 introgressed with *rymv1.2* resistance allele (IR64_R1.2) was used as resistant control. The lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles ; the upper vs. lower whisker extend from the hinge to the largest vs. smallest value no further than 1,5 x interquartile from the hinge. Different letters above the box-plots represent significant differences based on a Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by a Dunn post-hoc test (p-value < 0,5 after fdr correction).

Sup. Fig. 3 - Resistance of edited lines against isolates Cla, Ng106, Mg1 and Tz11.

Only lines resistant with isolated BF1 were tested with additional isolates. Symptoms observed 13 DAI and ELISA on leaf samples collected 13 (for Ng106 and Mg1) or 14 (for Cla and Tz11) DAI are represented. Kitaaake wild-type and IR64 were used as susceptibility controls ; IR64 introgressed with *rymv1.2* (IR64_R1.2) or *rymv1.3* (IR64_R1.3) resistance alleles were used as resistant controls. The lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles ; the upper vs. lower whisker extend from the hinge to the targets vs. smallest value no further than 1,5 x interquartile from the hinge. Different letters above the box-plots represent significant differences based on a Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by a Dunn post-hoc test (p -value $< 0,5$ after *fdr* correction).

Sup. Fig. 4 - Morphology of edited lines in controlled conditions.

Edited lines were evaluated for plant height at ripening stage in four independent experiments performed in controlled conditions. Results of three experiments are represented here, while results of the fourth one is presented in the main document. Fertiles tillers number was measured in two experiments and seed weight in a single one. The lower and upper hinges correspond to the first and third quartiles ; the upper vs. lower whisker extend from the hinge to the targets vs. smallest value no further than 1,5 x interquartile from the hinge. Different letters above the box-plots represent significant

differences based on a Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by a Dunn post-hoc test (p-value <0,5 after fdr correction).

Sup. Fig. 5 - Comparison between the predicted 3D model of the rice MIF4G domain (colored by pLDDT) and the crystallographic structure of human MIF4GII (PDB 1HU3, shown in red), displayed in side view. The predicted structure of the Kitaake MIF4G domain was superimposed onto the human MIF4GII crystal structure. As expected given the 32% sequence identity between the two proteins, they exhibited strong structural similarity with root mean square deviations (RMSD) below 2.5 Å. Notably, the two central helices 3a and 3b were predicted to form a longer hairpin in rice.

Sup. Fig. 6 - Predicted MIF4G 3D surface models of WT Kitaake and edited variants. All models were superimposed in the same orientation for comparison. Structures are colored according to per-residue model confidence score (pLDDT): dark blue (pLDDT>90) indicates

high-confidence regions; light blue (pI_{DDT}>80), confident regions; yellow (pI_{DDT}>60) and orange (pI_{DDT}>50), low-confidence regions.

Sup. Fig. 7 - Predicted 3D structure of MIF4G/VPg complex for WT Kitaake and edited variants, represented in side (a) and front (b) views. VPg and MIF4G are shown as ribbon and surface representations, respectively. The dotted frames highlight differences in VPg helix length and position among variants. For each view, all complexes were superimposed in the same orientation for comparison. The N-terminal domain of VPg was masked for clarity. Structures are colored according to per-residue model confidence score (pI_{DDT}): dark blue (pI_{DDT}>90) indicates high-confidence regions; light blue (pI_{DDT}>80), confident regions; yellow (pI_{DDT}>60) and orange (pI_{DDT}>50), low-confidence regions.

Sup. Fig. 8 - Conformational variability in the predicted 3D structures of the MIF4G domain for the *rymv1-3* allele alone (a, b) or in complex with RYMV VPg (c,d). Two out of five models showed a broken helix 3a (a, c) while it is not the case in the other three models (b, d). The MIF4G structures are colored according to per-residue model confidence score (pLDDT), with the following scheme: dark blue (pLDDT > 90) for high-confidence regions, light blue (pLDDT > 80) for confident regions, yellow (pLDDT > 60) for low-confidence regions, and orange (pLDDT > 50) for regions with the lowest confidence. The central helix of VPg is colored grey.